

A SWOT Analysis on Institutional Environments of University of the Punjab

Saghir Ahmad, Abid Hussain Ch., Atif Khalil, Misbah Malik

Abstract—The major purpose of the study was to identify the institutional environments' strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of University of the Punjab, Lahore. The target population of the study was teachers of University of the Punjab Lahore. The sample of 235 teachers (155 males, 80 females) were selected through multistage stratified sampling technique. A questionnaire regarding the institutional environments of University SWOT Analysis "Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats" was used to collect the required data for this study. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part comprised of the demographic information (faculty, department, gender, teacher rank), while the second part included the statements regarding SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats). Reliability index (Cronbach's Alpha) of the questionnaire was 0.87, which is statistically acceptable. Analysis of the data indicated that there was significant difference in the opinion of respondents. Teachers of Islamic studies and Laws had difference in their opinions regarding the institutional environment strengths, and opportunities and it was supported by the findings of the study. There was significant difference in opinions of male and female teachers regarding strengths and opportunities of university. And there was no significant difference in opinions of male and female teachers regarding weaknesses and threats of university.

Keywords—Institutional environments, SWOT analysis, teachers, University of the Punjab.

I. INTRODUCTION

STRATEGIC planning is characterized as an association's procedure of figuring its system in view of a careful analysis of its inner and outer circumstances. In correlation with strategic planning, strategic administration is an extensive procedure that incorporates strategic planning as well as ensuing steps, for example, system execution and assessment. Strategic administration comprises of four basic components: analysis of both internal and external environment, strategy design, its execution, assessment and control [1].

SWOT analysis is the main factor of strategic planning that is utilized for the scanning of institutional environments.

A. Saghir is PhD Scholar, Institute of Education and Research, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan. (Corresponding author, phone: +923067071099; e-mail: Saghir.edu786@gmail.com).

C. H. Abid, is Professor, Chairman with the Secondary Education Department at Institute of Education and Research, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan (e-mail: chabidhussainier@yahoo.com).

K. Atif, is PhD Scholar, Institute of Education and Research, University of the Punjab, Lahore, Pakistan (e-mail: ati.scholar@gmail.com).

M. Misbah is Lecturer with the Township Campus, University of Education, Lahore, Pakistan (e-mail: misbahmalik@ue.edu.pk).

SWOT analysis became prominent amongst the most mainstream instruments for key planning. SWOT is an acronym for Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats. It has its roots in 1960s, [2] and was promoted by the Wehrich's effort [3]. It is usually embraced for the scrutiny of interior and exterior circumstances, promising the improvement of plans which can compete with these circumstances. The use of this analysis has been testified for education institutions and in numerous other fields.

Strategic planning has turned into the viable way to deal with hierarchical administration in the greater part of associations in the innovative period, while the world has experienced real social, political, financial, innovative and demographic deviations. Universities also need to examine their surroundings both internal and external to recognize their qualities and inadequacies. SWOT examination is the recognized method to evaluate the current situation of an institution to make the future planning and the best decisions [4]-[7].

Higher education is considered backbone for getting success in every field of a society, nation and country. In this rapidly changing world, it has been a known reality that universities are being worked in a well ordered which needs of 21st era. We are confronting more change and the pace of progress is going to quicken for both governments and their endeavors in the twenty first century. Specifically, we provoke the contest of changing associations for which we shall have to change operators now [8].

Emerging nations are left with an impressive undertaking of extending their higher and advanced education frameworks by enhancing their worth in absence of environmental analysis and proceeding with economic limitations [9]. Educational institutions, colleges and universities are trying to adopt the process of strategic planning for the advancement of institution.

Education, particularly higher education, cannot stand separated from this worldwide marvel. Since the previous century, the scholastic segment has started to perceive that planning is essential to keep up its own responsiveness to speedily evolving surroundings [10]. Cameron [11] expressed that the fate of educational institutions depends upon new framework of managerial and institutional feedbacks. To endure and succeed in this challenging atmosphere, institutional pioneers are required to recognize their qualities, decrease their shortcomings, exploit the open doors of opportunities and minimize the impact of coercions. One straightforward, still viable path is to organize a SWOT inspection, a typical part of most vital and strategic plans [12].

Pakistan is facing challenges in planning process in the education sector. Therefore, to achieve a higher institutional performance, emphasis must be given to strategic planning process. There is a solid relation between effectiveness of education and strategic planning process. Effectiveness is merged with strategic planning when we use SWOT analysis comprehensively because it is a main component of strategic planning. To find out the strength, weaknesses, threats and opportunities is the actual work of SWOT analysis in the process of strategic planning [13].

This study will guide about SWOT analysis of the higher education, according to the prescribed rules and regulations for improving management abilities of the strategic planning process. The results of the study would provide valuable information for the design of SWOT analysis for the betterment of the strategic planning. It would also encourage the state educational policy makers to strengthen the strategic planning process in the system of education.

II. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine the internal and external institutional environments of University of the Punjab.
2. Identify the strengths of University of the Punjab.
3. Identify the weaknesses of University of the Punjab.
4. Identify the opportunities in University of the Punjab.
5. Identify the threats encountered by University of the Punjab.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Quantitative approach was employed for conducting the study. The study was descriptive and survey type in nature. The target population of the study consisted of teachers from University of the Punjab, recognized by the Higher Education Commission (HEC) located in Lahore. The study was conducted on university teachers by using multi-stage stratified random sampling technique. At the first stage, 13 faculties were selected by using stratified sampling technique from University of the Punjab. At the second stage, three departments were randomly selected from each faculty. At the third stage, 20 teachers were taken randomly as a sample from each faculty. In this way, total sample was depended on teachers respectively of University of the Punjab.

IV. INSTRUMENT OF THE STUDY

Questionnaire is a vital and well established research tool in social sciences research for acquiring information on participants' characteristics, knowledge, thoughts, experiences and their behavior [14]. For this study pre-developed questionnaire developed by Falk, [15] was adapted to collect the required information. The questionnaire consisted of two parts. The first part of the questionnaire contained demographic information (faculty, department, gender, teacher rank), while the second part consisted of statements regarding SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats) to know the perceptions of respondents. Likert-type

scale was used to respond each of the items setup as strongly agree, agree, to some extent, disagree and strongly disagree. Reliability index (Cronbach's Alpha) of the questionnaire was 0.87 which is statistically significant.

V. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

For the purpose of the data collection, the researchers visited the university. The questionnaire was distributed to the university teachers. Clear directions and instructions were given to the respondents regarding the questionnaire. But turnover rate of the respondents was a little bit less than the expected in the three faculties.

The data generated by instruments were tabulated and analyzed through Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS). According to the nature of research questions, descriptive statistics was used to obtain frequencies, mean, standard deviation. In inferential statistics, an independent sample t-test and one way ANOVA were applied.

TABLE I
DEMOGRAPHIC FILE ABOUT GENERAL INFORMATION NUMBER AND PERCENTAGE OF ALL FACULTIES' SELECTED TEACHERS OF UNIVERSITY

Teacher Ranks	N	Percentage (%)
Lecturer	82	35
Assistant Professor	75	32
Associate Professor	43	18
Professor	35	15

TABLE II
FREQUENCIES OF RESPONSES OF TEACHERS REGARDING POTENTIAL STRENGTHS OF UNIVERSITY

Sr.	Statements	M	SD
1	University provides curricular and co-curricular activities for the students.	4.38	.905
2	University offers civic engagement knowledge for the students.	3.89	.894
3	University provides opportunities to study abroad.	3.79	.903
4	University offers research based learning environment.	4.03	.816
5	University provides facilities for recreational activities.	3.95	.912
6	University has many Accredited Programs.	4.27	.858
7	University's campus is friendly and safe.	4.26	.933
8	University has significant impact on the regional community-educationally, economically, and culturally.	3.94	.833
9	University's facilities include new and well maintained, attractive buildings and grounds.	3.97	.942
10	Enrollment continues to increase in both undergraduate and graduate programs.	4.47	.741
11	University has an effective and supportive teaching and learning environment.	4.26	.683
12	University's workforce is stable and talented.	4.07	.759
13	University enjoys a positive reputation in the external community.	4.05	.780
14	University has a richness/diversity of disciplines and modes of thought and inquiry.	4.13	.845
15	Full-time faculty teaches the vast majority of classes, and there is a strong bond and a high level of interaction between faculty and students.	4.12	.794
16	University faculty, staff and students have a strong sense of community.	4.11	.777
17	University staff has engendering loyalty to institution, place, and coworkers.	4.06	.838
18	University is an economically sound and well managed institution.	4.16	.825

Table I indicates the ranks of teacher and percentage of

selected teachers. The first part of study based on teachers' perceptions of Punjab University. Table shows that there were 82 lecturers, 75 assistant professors, 43 associate professors and a few teachers were professors (35) participated in this study.

In Table II, statement one shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses about the strengths of university. High Mean value ($M = 4.38$, $SD = .905$) of the statement one shows that most teachers agree that the institution provides chances of curricular and co-curricular activities for the students. And all the other statements of Table II have mean scores almost near five. It means that according to university teachers, university has strengths related to civic engagement, knowledge for the students, opportunities to study abroad, research based learning environment, facilities for recreational activities, and accredited programs. The campus life is friendly and safe due to attractive buildings, grounds and natural, effective and supportive environment for teaching and learning. The institution is also enjoying the positive reputation in the external community. Due to this, foreigners take admission in university every year more than the year before. The major strength is that staff and students show their loyalty with institution. It is concluded that majority of the teachers of all faculties of university agree about strengths of Punjab University.

TABLE III
FREQUENCIES OF RESPONSES OF TEACHERS REGARDING POTENTIAL WEAKNESSES OF UNIVERSITY

Sr.	Statements	M	SD
1	University lacks of good governance, check and balance.	2.42	1.319
2	Most students have limited time and energy for their academic activities due to work and family commitments.	3.06	1.188
3	University has inconsistent academic advising structures and outdated curriculum.	2.30	1.214
4	Dispersal of data by organization should be reinforced and streamlined.	3.29	1.002
5	University lacks sufficient financial support for faculty scholarship.	2.87	1.076
6	University has higher tuition fee than other public institutions of the country.	2.12	1.137
7	Time demands on faculty limit their commitment to teaching and students.	3.32	1.037
8	Time demands on faculty necessarily constrain research, professional development, and training efforts.	3.29	1.025
9	Administrations offered by bolster workplaces are not sufficient, likely because of absence of fundamental staff, e.g., support for composing gifts, tending to consistence issues, and finishing building repairs in an opportune and financially savvy way, tending to issues with workstations and the data system, and so forth.	2.69	1.001
10	University has inadequate resources for recruitment, retention and advising of students.	2.97	1.097
11	Involvement of politics in administration, students and faculty.	3.97	.942
12	University lacks a strong mission, vision, and identity.	2.12	1.210
13	University is failing in judgment of market needs.	2.31	1.155
14	University has directionless research development and ineffective relationship with industry.	2.27	1.196
15	Improper/Misuse of funds and facilities.	2.64	1.128
16	Shortage of funds is hurdle to implementation of plans.	3.04	1.139

In Table III, statement one shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses about the weaknesses of university.

High Mean value ($M = 2.42$, $SD = 1.319$) of the statement one shows that most teachers do not agree that University lacks of good governance, check and balance. And all other statements of Table III have mean scores almost below three. According to teachers, there are no weaknesses of university like outdated curriculum, financial support for faculty scholarship, higher tuition fee, misuse of funds and facilities, and shortage of funds.

It is concluded that majority of the teachers of all faculties of university do not agree about weaknesses of Punjab University. Politics is one weakness which exists in institution.

TABLE IV
FREQUENCIES OF RESPONSES OF TEACHERS REGARDING POTENTIAL OPPORTUNITIES OF UNIVERSITY

Sr.	Statements	M	SD
1	The natural environment surrounding University is an important draw.	4.33	.692
2	More discussions and associations with neighborhood managers –those in the private, not-for-profit and open segments – could make our understudies additionally captivating to them.	4.07	.709
3	University's location offers opportunities to develop and support undergraduate and graduate programs.	4.14	.678
4	University takes advantage of its location, which may result in increased enrollments in strategically targeted programs.	4.09	.743
5	University could concentrate on incredibility with an accentuation on territories in which the grounds ought to develop.	4.00	.768
6	An undergraduate experience using the best practices from throughout the country could be developed.	4.02	.855
7	Collaborative methodologies could draw upon the qualities of various personnel, bolstered by asset and specialized staff, to offer more viable direction that likewise makes time for innovative work.	3.97	.816
8	Multimedia technology is changing the way of instructions by teachers in campus as well as generating new knowledge.	4.29	.796
9	Through multimedia, instructions are delivered and represents a significant opportunities to develop new and more effective ways of teaching and learning.	4.26	.821
10	Technology could greatly assist outreach efforts to meet the educational needs of place-bound students.	4.11	.791
11	University could build graduate understudy enlistments in those orders where there is departmental limit, and which won't unfavorably influence undergrad guideline.	3.95	.836
12	Turning into a pioneer in interdisciplinary and coordinated learning.	3.90	.898
13	Extended role of university in solving crisis and disasters (natural, men made).	3.88	.890
14	Deliberate and genuine utilization of execution appraisal, particularly of learning results, could prompt enhanced viability and effectiveness.	4.39	.647
15	Raising admission standards could enhance the normal educational capacity of the understudy body, bringing about enhanced maintenance also.	3.86	1.002
16	There is a growing interest in different countries such as China and Sudan for Pakistani Education; targeted efforts could help recruit full paying students from these countries.	4.01	.865

In Table IV, statement one shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses about the opportunities of university. High Mean value ($M = 4.33$, $SD = .692$) of the statement one shows that most teachers agree that natural environment surrounding university is an important draw. And all other statements of Table IV have mean scores almost near five. It is concluded that university has many opportunities for

the improvement of academic, administrative, financial and many other fields. According to teachers, university has opportunities to start the graduate and undergraduate programs in different disciplines, university has high qualify staff already and also in position to hire more teachers. There is multimedia technology used in departments of university to compete the trends and issues in academic field of 21st century. Teachers delivered their lectures through multimedia. The university is enjoying its status and opportunities in his country and also all over the world. There are a number of foreign students from various countries who take admission in different departments of university every year due to the positive reputation of the university.

It is concluded that majority of the teachers of all faculties of the university agreed about opportunities in the Punjab University. And due to these opportunities, university is enjoying its status not only in the whole country but also in the whole world.

TABLE V
FREQUENCIES OF RESPONSES OF TEACHERS REGARDING POTENTIAL THREATS OF UNIVERSITY

Sr.	Statements	M	SD
1	Declining assets from the nation and expanding reliance on educational cost income.	4.01	1.052
2	Declining monetary provision for students that lead to more pupils functioning to stay in school.	3.86	.902
3	K-12 students less prepared for university education.	3.76	1.028
4	Rapidly changing educational environment.	3.98	.882
5	Time-consuming and complex procedures of securing imperative endorsements for new projects.	3.69	.989
6	Development of authoritative and administration capacities required to be in consistence with (degenerate and unreasonably) commands.	3.00	1.177
7	Loss of open backing and moving mentalities toward the other university.	2.53	1.224
8	Diminishing capacity to vie for and hold top personnel.	2.54	1.272
9	On-line academic system has been introduced in other universities.	3.60	1.030
10	Declining number of college graduate students.	3.05	1.116
11	University's teachers and students participate in politics.	3.61	.920
12	University has incompetent and outdated management.	2.31	1.257
13	Rapid expansion of private universities.	3.52	1.043
14	Brain Drain in government university.	3.41	1.138
15	HEC Body is losing its recognition.	2.66	1.149
16	Less pay is provided in government university.	2.74	1.163

In Table V, statement one shows the mean and standard deviation of the responses about the strengths of university. High mean value (M = 4.01, SD = 1.052) of the statement one shows that most teachers agree that assets of country are decreasing due to which educational institutions charge the extra fee from students. And all other statements of Table V have mean scores almost four or near four. It shows that university is facing some threats e.g. changes in education environment, the online academic system which has been introduced in many universities, and institutional politics is increasing day by day among teachers and students. The private universities are opening which enhances the competition level among institutions. The results also show that private institutions offer high salary packages and many

other facilities to faculty members, and skilled teachers of university are moving from public to private institutions.

It is concluded that majority of the teachers of all faculties of the university were unanimous about above mentioned threats of Punjab University. There are some threats like incompetent and outdated management of university, HEC (Higher Education Commission) body is losing its recognition, and less pay is provided in public sector universities. Most teachers of the university disagreed with these threats, however.

TABLE VI
INDEPENDENT SAMPLE T-TEST FOR DIFFERENCE OF STRENGTHS, WEAKNESSES, OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS OF UNIVERSITY ON THE BASIS OF MALE AND FEMALE TEACHERS

Factors	Gender	N	M	SD	t-value	df	Sig.
Potential strengths	Male	155	4.0616	.49296	-2.275	197.440	.024
	Female	80	4.1944	.38368			
Potential weaknesses	Male	155	2.8105	.60748	.643	233	820
	Female	80	2.7562	.62402			
Potential opportunities	Male	155	4.0319	.43903	-2.857	213.500	.005
	Female	80	4.1719	.30432			
Potential threats	Male	155	3.2891	.56444	.888	233	.406
	Female	80	3.2234	.47969			

In Table VI, in statement one, independent sample t-test was applied to compare the Strengths scores for males and females. There was significant difference in scores between males (M = 4.0616, SD = .49296) and females, M = 4.1944, SD = .38368; $t(-2.275) = 197.440, p = .024$.

In statement 2, independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the Weaknesses scores for males and females. There was no significant difference in scores between males (M = 2.8105, SD = .60748) and females, M = 2.7562, SD = .62402; $t(.643) = 233, p = 820$.

In statement 3, independent sample t-test was applied to compare the Opportunities scores for males and females. There was significant difference in scores between males (M = 4.0319, SD = .43903) and females, M = 4.1719, SD = .30432; $t(-2.875) = 213.500, p = .005$.

In statement 4, independent sample t-test was conducted to compare the Threats scores for males and females. There was no significant difference in scores between males (M = 3.2891, SD = .56444) and females, M = 3.2234, SD = .47969; $t(.888) = 233, p = .406$.

It is concluded that there was significant difference in their perception scores between male and female teachers of the university regarding the institutional environment strengths, and opportunities. And there was no significant difference in their perception scores between male and female teachers of the university regarding the institutional environment weaknesses and threats.

An analysis of variance test applied for the difference in mean scores of teachers' perceptions related to strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of Punjab University.

Perceptions were measured in four areas i.e. the strengths of university; $F(12, 222) = 5.477, p = .000$; university weaknesses: $F(12, 222) = 6.660, p = .000$; university opportunities: $F(12, 222) = 5.134, p = .000$; and university

threats: $F(12, 222) = 2.677, p = .002$. There was statistically significant difference in the results of four areas. It means that teachers of the Punjab University had different perceptions regarding strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of university.

TABLE VII
ANOVA FOR THE DIFFERENCE IN THE MEAN SCORES OF TEACHERS BY SELECTED FACULTIES ON UNIVERSITY'S STRENGTHS, WEAKNESSES, OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS

Factors	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Potential strengths	11.417	12	.951	5.477	.000
	38.566	222	.174		
	49.983	234			
Potential weaknesses	23.227	12	1.936	6.660	.000
	64.522	222	.291		
	87.749	234			
Potential opportunities	8.262	12	.689	5.134	.000
	29.771	222	.134		
	38.033	234			
Potential threats	8.529	12	.711	2.677	.002
	58.940	222	.265		
	67.469	234			

TABLE VIII
ANOVA FOR DIFFERENCE IN THE MEAN SCORES OF TEACHERS ON UNIVERSITY'S STRENGTHS, WEAKNESSES, OPPORTUNITIES AND THREATS

Factors	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Potential strengths	1.689	3	.563	2.693	.047
	48.294	231	.209		
	49.983	234			
Potential weaknesses	1.118	3	.373	.994	.396
	86.631	231	.375		
	87.749	234			
Potential opportunities	.423	3	.141	.866	.459
	37.610	231	.163		
	38.033	234			
Potential threats	2.199	3	.733	2.594	.053
	65.270	231	.283		
	67.469	234			

An analysis of variance test applied for the difference in mean scores of Lecturer, Assistant Professor, Associate Professor and Professor' perceptions related to strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats of Punjab University.

Perceptions were measured in four areas i.e. university Strengths; $F(3, 231) = 2.693, p = .047$; university Weaknesses: $F(3, 231) = .994, p = .396$; university Opportunities: $F(3, 231) = .866, p = .459$; and university Threats: $F(3, 231) = 2.594, p = .053$. There was statistically significant difference in the opinions of teachers regarding strengths and there was no significant difference in the perceptions of teachers related to weaknesses, opportunities and threats of university. It means that teachers of various ranks in the Punjab University had different perceptions regarding strengths, and almost had same perceptions regarding weaknesses, opportunities and threats of university.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present study was conducted to have a clear picture of the SWOT analysis regarding the institutional environments of university. The sample of the study was teachers of University of the Punjab, Lahore. It is concluded that respondents of the study had significant difference in their opinions. There was significant difference in perceptions between teachers of university regarding the institutional environment strengths, and opportunities. And there was no significant difference in perceptions between teachers of university regarding the institutional environment weaknesses and threats. The teachers of Islamic studies and Law department had significant difference in their opinions and they disagreed from other teachers of all faculties related to university strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

The SWOT analysis can be basic or complex subject to the particular institutional circumstances. For Punjab University, to face numerous difficulties posed by globalization and the new market-driven economy, the university needs to create strategic planning approach, and SWOT ought to be the first precise endeavor to develop strategic planning. It is confirmed that the universities of 21st century will succeed when they can react to social needs with skilled programs and quality academic atmosphere [16]. In the education field, it is compulsory for executives and plan makers to think and make plans strategically. In the setting of the quickly evolving world, this will be essential for institutional survival and flourishing.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wheelen, T. L., & Hunger, J. D. 1995. *Strategic management and business policy*, (5th ed.). Addison Wesley, Reading, MA.
- [2] Learned, E. P., Christensen, C. R., Andrews, K. E., & Guth, W. D. 1965. *Business Policy: Text and cases*. Irwin, Homewood, IL.
- [3] Wehrich, H. 1982. The TOWS matrix: A tool for situational analysis, *Long Range Planning*, 15(2), 54-66.
- [4] Ansoff, H. I. 1965. *Corporate strategy*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [5] Andrew, K. R. 1987. *The concept of corporate strategy*. Irwin, Homewood, IL.
- [6] Porter, M. E. 1991. Toward a Dynamic Theory of Strategy. *Strategic Management Journal* 1(2), 5-11.
- [7] Mintzberg, H., Ahlstrand, B., & Lampel, J. 1998. *Strategy Safari*, Pearson Education, Harlow.
- [8] Stace, D., & Dunphy, D. C. 2001. *Beyond the boundaries: Leading and re-creating the successful enterprise* (2nd ed.). McGraw Hills: Sydney.
- [9] World Bank, 2000. Retrieved from <http://www.google.com>.
- [10] Kriemadis, A. 1997. Strategic planning in higher education athletic departments. *International Journal of Educational Management*, 11(6), 238-247.
- [11] Cameron, K. 1983. Strategic responses to conditions of decline in higher education and private sector. *Journal of Higher Education*, 54(4), 359-380.
- [12] Schneider, S. C., & Meyer, D. A. 1991. Interpreting and responding to strategic issues: The impact of national culture. *Strategic Management Journal*, 12(1), 307-320.
- [13] Kotler, P. 2000. *Marketing Management*, Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- [14] Bulmer, M. 2004. Questionnaires, *SAGE Benchmarks in Social Research Methods*. (1st ed.). London: SAGE Publications Ltd.
- [15] Falk, D. 2011. Strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats; *Draft, UMD SWOT Preliminary Results*.
- [16] Navarro, J. R., & Gallardo, F. O. 2003. A model of strategic change: Universities and dynamic capabilities. *Higher Education Policy*, 16(1), 199-212.